

Flower identification using deep neural network – Bloom:

There are thousands of species of plant & flowers & it's very difficult for any individual to remember each & every flower with precise details however currently there is no any reliable application for students & researchers to identify flowers with reliable results.

The reason behind it is that Deep Learning Algorithms required much specified, high quality & precisely labelled data. While there are still chances of error because of similarity in flowers so we captured images with specific methods to gain a high-quality dataset. In this project, we initialize a model that can identify plant flowers with reliable prediction according to a specific data-gathering technique. First of all, we gathered data in different time periods (day-light & evening) & Angles - entire plant, flower frontal- and, flower top. We gathered 10 classes of data in this initial project & for each class, there are approximately 200 images.

First, we trained the model on SSD MobnetV2 Algorithm so that we can make Android Application but the results were not satisfying, so later the object detection Algorithm we used is Faster R-CNN with Inception V2. We design a model in a way that it can classify an image with localization so that it can identify multiple flowers in a single image even of different classes. Our final aim was to train data set on 200000 steps using GPU. The Results were satisfying with up to 100% accuracy confidence & 86.3 % mAP (mean Average Precision)

After successfully training the model, we deployed the model on Web Application using the Django framework. Currently, the Web application is deployed on local host soon we will make it live on www.

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Results & Screenshot of project:

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